

Hydrogen Bonding in Aromatic Aldehydes and Acetophenones

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Ultra-violet spectra of hydroxy-; halo-; nitro-; nitro, halo-; and nitro, hydroxy-benzaldehydes and hydroxy, halo-acetophenones have been reported in polar and non-polar solvent to distinguish the presence of the strong and a weak intra-molecular hydrogen bond.

The absorption spectra of organic compounds, having an intramolecular hydrogen bond have been distinguished by Korobkov¹⁶ in two types : (i) strong and (ii) weak.

There are contradictory reports, about the presence of an intramolecular hydrogen bond in 2-nitrobenzaldehyde^{2a,b} and 2-halo phenols^{3,23} and its absence in 2-nitrobenzaldehyde^{7,12,18} and 2-halophenols¹³.

The formation of the weak intramolecular hydrogen bond, between hydrogen of aldehydic group and *o*-nitro-, or *o*-halo-group in *o*-substituted benzaldehydes, was regarded as an unusual kind of hydrogen bond²¹; and supported by the following facts: (a) the

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hydrogen bond thus formed has low energy (2 K.cal); (b) the steric interaction between the formyl and *o*-nitro-group causes, the increase in frequencies in I. R. and (c) the values for displacement of p.p.m. in N. M. R. spectra of nitrobenzene by 2-hydroxy group in 2-nitro phenol compared with 2-hydroxy group in 2-nitro benzaldehyde is $6\frac{1}{2}$ times high and attributed to strong hydrogen bond.

The solvent effect, studied by Baliah and coworkers^{1, a, b} and Bayliss et al², showed that the absorption bands of nonchelating compounds shifted towards longer wavelength in polar solvent. This criterion has been used in this paper to distinguish strong and weak hydrogen bond.

The numbering of the bands adopted here is similar to Braude⁴. Braude and Soundheimer⁵ and Morton and Stubbs¹⁹ recorded three bands for benzaldehyde in cyclohexane at (242, 248 m μ) K, band; (280, 289 m μ) B, band, and (328, 338, 353 and 370 m μ) as R band. Dearden and Forbes¹¹ observed only two latter bands.

4-Bromobenzaldehyde¹ showed absorption bands very similar to *p*-chlorobenzaldehyde¹³. The displacements to the longer wavelength is due to resonance structures.

The aldehyde (17) and acetophenones (5,6) showed absorption for carbonyl group and comparable with the spectra of *p*-hydroxy benzaldehyde and *p*-hydroxy acetophenone,^{19,20} respectively.

For 2-Chloro-; 2, 4-dibromo-; 2-chloro , 4-nitro-; and 2-bromo, 4-nitro-benzaldehyde in methanol absorption bands were observed at 250, 268, 268 and 268 m/ μ whereas in cyclohexane at 250, 265, 266 and 267.5 m/ μ respectively. This confirms the previous findings, 13, 21 (a-c) of the presence of a weak intramolecular hydrogen bond between hydrogen of aldehydic group and halogen in *o*-position. The bathochromic shifts is attributed to the presence of substituent in *p*-position¹³.

2-Hydroxy-; 2-hydroxy,5-chloro-; 2-hydroxy, 5-bromobenzaldehydes and 2-hydroxy, 5-chloro and 2-hydroxy, 5-bromoacetophenones showed distinct K-, B-, and R-bands. The main bands of spectra of 2-hydroxybenzaldehydes in ethanol and in cyclohexane found to be identical¹³ where as R-band absorbs at longer wavelength in cyclohexane.

2-Hydroxy, 3-chlorobenzaldehyde did not show any change of absorption in different solvents showing the formation of strong hydrogen bond between aldehydic and hydroxy groups.¹⁷

2-Hydroxy, 3-bromobenzaldehyde showed bathochromic shift in cyclohexane probably due to steric hindrance of bromine. The spectra of hydroxy halo acetophenones, as anticipated showed hypochromic effects with no change in wavelengths of absorption bands.

For 2-Hydroxy, 3-nitro-, and 2-hydroxy, 5-nitrobenzaldehydes the former shows the formation of strong hydrogen bond, as its spectra in ethanol and cyclohexane do not differ; whereas latter in ethanol, records considerable displacement towards longer wavelength; very similar to *m*-nitrobenzaldehyde¹². This is in excellent agreement, with Hoyer and Hensel's¹⁵ and Forsen and Akermark¹⁴ results that in 3-nitro, 2-hydroxy acetophenone, hydrogen of hydroxy group chelates with both formyl and nitro groups but predominantly bonded towards the nitro group (I) rather than the formyl group (II)

Of 2-nitro-, 2-nitro, 4-chloro-, and 2-nitro, 4-bromo-benzaldehydes, the absorption bands in cyclohexane except the last appeared at the slightly longer wavelengths compared with the same in ethanol (table 1.); indicating the absence of very weak hydrogen bond.^{1,2}

The present studies confirm :

- (a) The presence of a strong hydrogen bond in *o*-hydroxy benzaldehydes and *o*-hydroxy-acetophenones ; when there is no strong competing group, adjacent to hydroxy group;
- (b) The intra molecular hydrogen bond can be easily identified in chelated, and non-chelated compounds by a comparison of the spectra in ethanol and cyclohexane; in the former it is nearly identical whereas in the latter it shows bathochromic shift in alcohol.

The solvent effect i.e. intermolecular association, intermolecular charge transfer²¹ which is related to the corresponding $\eta \rightarrow \pi$ transitions²² of *carbonyl* group in aldehyde and ketone, and substitution by other groups needs to be taken in to consideration;

- (c) The values of inter atomic distances and bond angles in the six membered chelate compounds are such as to favour the formation of a strong hydrogen bond. In chelates with five membered ring, these conditions are not favourable.

EXPERIMENTAL

Ultraviolet absorption measurements were made in ethanol and cyclohexane (BDH) using Hilger's U. V. spectrophotometer.

The compounds, if liquid purified by fractional distillation and solid recrystallised from suitable solvent until constant m.p. was attained.

TABLE I
Absorption Spectra of Aldehydes.

No.	Band	K	Alcohol	B	R	K	B	R
	-benzaldehyde	λ_{\max} log ϵ	Cyclohexane λ_{\max} log ϵ	λ_{\max} log ϵ				
		max	max	max	max	max	max	max
1.	4-Hydroxy 3-methoxy 5-bromo-	238 (4.182)	—	298 (4.019)	—	—	—	—
2.	4-Bromo	—	255 (4.053) 250 (4.068)	262 (4.064)	270 (4.101)	—	257 (4.073) 262 (4.333)	—
3.	2-Chloro	—	250 (3.793) 256 (3.763)	260sh (3.647)	—	301.5 (3.073)	250 (3.878)	301. (3.76)
4.	2-Hydroxy, 5-nitro-	239 (4.176)	244 (4.184)	—	315 (3.999)	—	295 (3.766)	—
5.	2,4-Dibromo	266 (3.922)	—	—	268 (3.715)	—	265 (3.116)	—
6.	2-bromo, 4-nitro-	299 (3.869)	256sh (3.875)	263 (3.886)	270.5 (3.861)	—	267.5 (4.005)	—
7.	2-Hydroxy-	228 (3.568)	250 (3.535) 255 (3.608)	—	—	326.5 (3.573)	255 (3.637) 262 (3.625)	339. (3.197)
8.	2-Hydroxy, 5-bromo-	230 (4.235)	255.5 (3.924)	260.5 (3.862)	—	350 (3.909)	215 (3.683)	352 (3.287)
9.	2-Hydroxy, 3,5-dibromo-	228 (4.777)	256(4.178) 251 (4.163)	260 (4.127)	—	349 (3.771)	262 (4.219) 257 (4.180)	352 (3.830)
10.	2-Hydroxy, 3-chloro-	225 (4.107)	250 (3.937) 256 (4.061)	262 (4.080) 267 (4.007)	—	341 (3.568)	261 (4.177) 267 (3.918)	345 (3.708)
11.	-Hydroxy, 5-chloro-	236.5 (3.546)	256 (3.456) 250 (3.480)	261 (3.416)	290 (3.103)	348 (3.244)	257 (3.876) 262 (3.755)	353 (3.364)
12.	2-Hydroxy, 3-bromo-	228 (3.933)	248 (4.033)	—	—	356 (3.319)	272 (3.810)	362 (3.458)
13.	2-Hydroxy, 3-nitro-	238 (4.137)	240 (4.149)	—	—	365 (2.669)	240 (4.237)	357 (3.495)
14.	2-Chloro, 4-nitro-	239 (4.176)	244 (4.184)	268 (3.832)	—	315 (3.899)	266 (2.866)	295 (3.766)
15.	2-Nitro-	226 (3.797)	250 (3.618) 255 (3.625)	261 (3.600) calc	—	—	252 (3.869)	—
16.	2-Nitro, 4-chloro	230 (3.914)	255 (3.667)	261 (3.682)	—	—	258 (3.163)	—
17.	2-Nitro, 4-bromo	224 (3.852)	259 (3.868) 252 (3.818)	265 (3.917)	293sh(4.179)	—	296 (4.012)	—
18.	<i>p</i> -Hydroxy-	221 (4.14)	—	—	2840 (4.24)	—	—	—

Sh=shoulder

Calc=calculated.

TABLE II
Acetophenones.

No	Band	Alcohol			Cyclohexane			
		K	B	R	K	B	R	
	-acetophenone	$\lambda_{\max} \log \epsilon_{\max}$						
1.	2--Hydroxy, 3-bromo-	225 (3.994)	250 (4.022)	261 (3.934)	335 (2175)	226 (3.355)	253 (3.19)	335 (2.801)
2.	2-Hydroxy, 5-Bromo-	230 (3.916)	250 (3.769) 255 (3.719)	260 (3.570)	350 (3.484)	230 (3.921)	252 (3.60)	352 (3.31)
3.	2-Hydroxy, 3-chloro-	229 (3.708)	256 (3.711) 250 (3.77)	262 (3.274) 267 (3.658)	340 (2.55)	225 (3.098)	260 (2.955)	335 (2.611)
4.	3-Hydroxy 5-Chloro-	229 (3.810)	250 (3.702) 255 (3.681)	260 (3.496)	349 (3.478)	228 (3.999)	252 (3.655)	354 (3.207)
5.	4-Hydroxy, 5-chloro-	228 (4.069)	—	276 (4.068)	—	—	—	—
6.	4-Hydroxy, 5-bromo-	229 (4.229)	calc. 256 (3.735)	262 (3.75)	—	—	—	—

The aldehydes (table No. I,II)¹⁰ and (5-8)⁸ have been prepared by Beech's method; (10,11,13 and 14)⁹ by Riemer-Tiemann's method, 5-bromo-and 3, 5-dibromosalicylaldehydes by bromination of salicylaldehyde, while 3-methoxy, 4-hydroxy, 5-bromobenzaldehyde that of vanillin and nitrohydroxybenzaldehydes by nitration of salicylaldehyde. The halogeno acetophenones (table No. II) (1-6)^{9,10} were obtained by Fries reaction from acetyl derivative of corresponding halogenophenol.